

Anthraquinone glycoside from *Elaeagnus umbellata* Thunb.

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Manuscript received 15 May 2001, revised 23 August 2001, accepted 25 September 2001

A new anthraquinone glycoside identified as 1,6-dihydroxy-2-methyl-8-O- β -D-glycopyranosyl(1 \rightarrow 6)- α -L-xylopyranoside anthraquinone with two known compounds betulin and quercetin have been isolated from the arial parts of *Elaeagnus umbellata*.

Elaeagnus umbellata Thunb. (Elaeagnaceae) is a small deciduous thorny shrub, used as an astringent¹. Edward *et al.*² reported a large number of flavonoids for cytotoxic activity. *Elaeagnus* species have been investigated for flavonoids³ and terpenoids⁴. Potter and Thomas⁵ isolated palmitic acid, fatty acids (C₁₄-C₂₀) methyl ester, eugenol-1-methylphenol, phenylacetaldehyde and 2-nonenol from the floral parts of *E. umbellata*. The present study describes isolation and structure elucidation of a new glycoside besides betulin and quercetin glycoside.

Results and Discussion

The aqueous ethanolic extract of arial parts of *E. umbellata* on repeated CC over silica gel afforded compound 1, 2 and 3. Compounds 1 and 2 were identified as betulin and quercetin-3-O-glucoside by comparison with authentic sample and reported data⁶.

Compound 3, a colourless crystalline solid, m.p. 227–229° (MeOH) showed molecular ion peak at *m/z* 571 [M]⁺ and 572 [M + H]⁺ in its FAB-MS. The peak at *m/z* 651 and 471 arose by the loss of one hexose and one pentose, respectively. The UV spectrum showed absorption at 218, 225, 305 and 315 nm. Its IR spectrum displayed characteristic band for chelated carbonyl group at 1625 cm⁻¹. ¹³C NMR of 3 showed presence of twentyseven carbon atoms. The assignment of all proton and carbon were achieved by ¹H-¹H HOMO (DQF-COSY) and inverse ¹³C-¹H correlated 2D-NMR (HMQC) spectra. ¹³C NMR data showed anthraquinone moiety.

The anomeric proton of 3 exhibited doublet at δ 5.89 (*J* 7.2 Hz, anomeric proton of β linked D-glucose). A doublet at δ 4.620 (*J* 2.8 Hz) was assigned for α -linked xylose. In the ¹³C NMR of 3, C-6 of glucose showed a downfield shift at δ 62.32 while a slightly shielded C-5 resonance at δ 77.06 was assigned for glycosidic linkage at C-6 of glucose. The downfield signals at δ 142.2, 142.8, 158.19 and 153.18 were assigned for substituted C-1, C-2, C-6 and C-8 carbon atoms, C-8 found to be glycosilated.

Experimental

M.ps. were uncorrect. UV spectra were taken in MeOH. ¹H NMR spectra were taken using TMS as internal standard and CDCl₃ and CD₃OD as solvent; all the signals are expressed as δ values downfield from TMS. CC was carried out on silica gel 60–120 mesh (Merck). The leaves of *E. umbellata* were collected from Phata Rudraprayag, Uttaranchal, India, and identified by Department of Botany, H. N. B. Garhwal University, Srinagar. The air-dried leaves of the plant were exhaustively extracted with 90% aqueous EtOH for 72 h. The extract was concentrated to dryness. Repeated CC afforded compounds 1 (0.5 g), 2 (0.7 g) and 3 (0.35 g). Compounds 1 and 2 were identified as betulin and quercetin glycoside by their reported data.

Compound 3 : Colourless crystalline sold, m.p. 227–229° (MeOH); λ_{max} 222, 254, 280, 410 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3240, 3040, 1895, 1660, 1450, 1250, 1190, 915 and 850 cm⁻¹; FABMS *m/z* 571 [M]⁺, 409 [M-162], 257 [M-(162 + 132)]; δ 3.8 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.55 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, H-3), 6.95 (1H, dd, *J* 7.8, 1.8 Hz, H-7), 7.76 (dd, *J* 7.6, 1.8 Hz, H-5), 7.28 (d, *J* 1.2 Hz, H-4), glucose δ 5.8 (d, *J* 7.2 Hz, H-1'), 3.19 (m), 3.37 (m), 3.46 (m), 3.63 (dd, *J* 5.6 Hz, H-6'),

xylose δ 4.620 (d, J 2 Hz, H-1''); ^{13}C NMR 142.2 (C-1), 142.8 (C-2), 124.2 (C-3), 124.16 (C-4), 112.7 (C-5), 151.2 (C-6), 123.2 (C-7), 158.19 (C-8), 180.23 (C-9), 179.2 (C-10), 138.09 (C-11), 113.3 (C-12), 114.1 (C-13), 139.08 (C-14), 29.9 (CH_3), glycone 104.82 (C-1'), 74.56 (C-2'), 77.68 (C-3'), 71.06 (C-4'), 77.06 (C-5'), 62.32 (C-6'), xylose 102.98 (C-1''), 74.07 (C-2''), 74.9 (C-3''), 71.8 (C-4''), 61.9 (C-5'').

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Professor Y. Takeda, Japan, for recording spectra. One of the authors (S.C.S.) is grateful to D.S.T., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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